

Self-Healing Fibre Reinforced Polymer Composites – A Bristol Perspective

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Damage in FRPs

- FRPs finding widespread deployment in diverse applications.
- Reticence in using FRP in safety critical applications – defect sensitivity!
- 'no damage growth' current mindset
 - Excessive weight
 - Shackling of innovative design
 - Need for frequent inspection

Damage in FRPs

- Time for step change in philosophy
- Allow (some) damage growth to be tolerated
- Considerable weight/cost saving
- Freedom to incorporate new functions

B.J. Blaiszik et al. *Annu. Rev. Mater. Res.* 40 2010.

Images courtesy of Dr Emile Greenhalgh, Imperial College London

Images courtesy of Dr Stephen Hallett, ACCIS, University of Bristol

Self-Healing - Concept

B.J. Blaiszik et al. *Annu. Rev. Mater. Res.* 2010. 40:179–211

Self-Healing - Approaches

B.J. Blaiszik et al. *Annu. Rev. Mater. Res.* 2010. 40:179–211

Microcapsules

Patel et al. 2010

Vasculs

Norris et al. 2011

Intrinsic

Pingkarawat et al. 2012

Liquid self-healing agent delivery approaches

Self-Healing - Intrinsic

Healing of FRP containing particles or fibres of mendable thermoplastic poly[ethylene-co-(methacrylic acid)] (EMAA)

Fig. 12. EMAA ligaments bridging a delamination crack following five healing cycles.

- Thermally activated - large increase in interlaminar fracture toughness, repeated healing
- Inherent pressure delivery mechanism, via presence of bubbles and viscous flow

Pingkarawat et al.; *J Mater Sci* (2012) 47:4449–4456

Varley & Charve; *Composites Part* (2012) 43(7):1073–1080

Pingkarawat et al.; *Composites Part A* (2012) 43(8):1301–1307

Self-Healing - Intrinsic

- Thermo-reversible material with 'soft' thermoplastic and 'hard' thermoplastic behaviours
- Compatibility with epoxy-based FRP systems
- Easy to process ($\sim 120-150^\circ\text{C}$)
- >50% recovery (5 mins @ 150°C)

Functionality to turn on/off bismaleimide cross-linking to achieve structural recovery

Turkenburg, D.H., et al., *Diels-Alder based, thermo-reversible cross-linked epoxies for use in self-healing composites*. *Polymer*, 2015, 79, p. 187-194.

Coope, T.S., et al., *Novel Diels-Alder based self-healing epoxies for aerospace composites*. *Smart Materials and Structures*, 2016, 25, 084010 (9pp).

Self-Healing - Microencapsulation

An integrated microcapsule based SH system tailored for FRP composite materials.

Dispersed, monomer filled microcapsules, **decorated** with catalyst:

- Crack formed damage event.
- Propagating crack ruptures microcapsules, releases monomer.
- Healing agent polymerises after contact with catalyst coating and repairs damage.

Microcapsules with UF/PU shell, liquid monomer core, catalyst coating.

*Crushed
microcapsules
bond glass
slides*

Self-Healing – Vascular Networks

Nature's approach to transporting functional agents.

- Potential to deliver **large volumes**.
- Agent not required to **survive FRP manufacturing**.
- **Replenishable**

HR Williams, et al. *J. Roy. Soc. Interface.* 2008. 5:735-747..
 HR Williams, et al. *J. Roy. Soc. Interface.* 2008. 5:55-65.

Self-Healing – Vascular Networks

Self-Healing – Vascular Networks

Arrows indicate
resin infusion
direction

Strategy for implementation

Design for manufacturability

Intrinsic: Diels-Alder (DA) epoxy-based self-healing system

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Intrinsic: Diels-Alder (DA) epoxy-based self-healing system

- Dry fibres infused with DA prepolymer in hot press (150°C, 5 min)
- DA self-healing prepreg (SHpp) located on central mid-plane (UD)
- Multiple healing cycles (150°C, 5 min)
 - 1st healing cycle: 45%
 - 2nd healing cycle: 50%
 - 3rd healing cycle: 65%
- Homogeneous integration with host matrix (Gurit SE70, 100°C cure)

Design for performance

Extrinsic: Embedded vascular channels

- SH in skin-stringer test panel (Gurit SE70 OOA)
- Microvascular channels (~250 μm)
- Connectivity along skin-stringer interface after damage
- Post failure - inject premixed in-house developed toughened epoxy resin
- Thermal cure cycle applied (65°C/1 hr)

- Initial failure via delamin. of stiffener @ ~70kN
- 'Healed' failure via delam. of stiffener @ ~90kN
- High recovery of stiffness post-healing

R Luterbacher, TS Coope, RS Trask, IP Bond, *Vascular self-healing within carbon fibre reinforced polymer stringer run-out configurations*, Comp. Sci. Tech. 2016, 136, 67-75
 Everitt DT, Luterbacher R, Coope TS, Trask RS, Wass DF, Bond IP, *Optimisation of epoxy blends for use in extrinsic self-healing fibre-reinforced composites*, Polymer, 69, 2015, 283-292 .

Self-Healing – Healing Agent

Desirable properties?

- Good mechanical properties – stiff, strong, compliant
- Excellent healing function - gap-filling/expanding volume
- Compatibility with FRP matrix;
 - Adhesion and toughness
 - Low viscosity for infiltration of damage
- Life-time, comparable with component life
- High reactivity for cure under any conditions.
- Stoichiometry independent
- Delivery mechanism independent - microcapsule, microvascule
- Compatibility with composites manufacturing & processes

Coope TS, Wass DF, Trask RS, Bond IP; Metal Triflates as Catalytic Curing Agents in Self-Healing Fibre Reinforced Polymer Composite Materials . *Macromol. Mater. Eng.* 2014, 299, 208–218
Everitt DT, Luterbacher R, Coope TS, Trask RS. Wass DF, Bond IP; Optimisation of epoxy blends for use in extrinsic self-healing fibre-reinforced composites. *Polymer* 69 (2015) 283-292

Self-Healing – Challenges

**FRP composite
manufacture**

**Volume
generation**

**Fracture
debris**

**Damage
visualisation**

**Healing agent
compatibility**

**Healing agent
viscosity**

**Healing agent
cure time**

**Healing agent
performance**

Self-Healing - Capability

B.J. Blaiszik et al. *Annu. Rev. Mater. Res.* 2010. 40:179–211

- Multiple mechanisms of SH for FRPs.
 - Intrinsic
 - Microcapsules
 - Vasculcs
- Significant recovery in mech. properties >80%.
- Removal of all damage not critical?
- **Need to match healing potential to damage!!**
- **Healing agent characteristics are KEY!!**

Self-Healing - Applications

Ply drop

- Ply drops & butt joints damage initiation points
- Embed microcapsules at features to heal on damage initiation.

Stiffener runout

- Failure of stiffener run-outs either in substrate or bondline
- Vasculs on non-toughened interfaces

T-joint

- Failures in deltoid, overlamine, interface
- Microcapsules and vasculs in deltoid

Stiffener Runout

T-Joints

Open Holes

Ply Drops

Cullinan JF, Wisnom MR, Bond IP. *Damage Manipulation and In Situ Repair of Composite T-Joints*. AIAA Journal of Aircraft 2016, 53(4), 1013-1021
 Cullinan J, Wisnom M, Bond I, Velut P, Michaud V. *In-situ repair of composite sandwich structures using cyanoacrylates*. Composites A. 2016, 87, pp.203-211
 Luterbacher Mus R, Trask R, Coope T, Bond. *Vascular self-healing within carbon fibre reinforced polymer stringer run-out configurations*. Comp. Sci. Tech. 2016, 136, 67-75

[R Luterbacher et al., UoB]

[S Hallett et al., UoB]

Remodelling & Regeneration

“Every change in the form and function of ... bone[s] or of their function alone is followed by certain definite changes in their internal architecture, and equally definite secondary alterations in their external conformation, in accordance with mathematical laws.”

J. Wolff as quoted by Keith 1918 [1]

- **Osteocytes** sense mechanical loading
- **Osteoclasts** remove old bone
- **Osteoblasts** follow osteoclasts and form new bone

Future Challenge: Can we create something as good as this?

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Questions?

